

SOCIAL PROBLEMS OF RAISING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM

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Annotation

social problems of raising young people in Uzbekistan in the spirit of military patriotism in our article. The changing view of the concept of Homeland in globalistic processes. Meditating on views between patriotism and military patriotism.

Keywords

patriotism, military patriotism, Global, Nation.

Patriotism means love and loyalty to the motherland, service to the motherland and the happiness of his whole life and potential along the way, and, if necessary, self-sacrifice. Patriotism is one of the universal feeling, spiritual values, common to all people, Nations, peoples, polished for centuries.

Historically, patriotism is also a set of emotions that have been improved in the process of socio-economic development, the struggle of peoples towards the inviolability and independence of the territory in which they live, associated with the fate of their homeland. It is manifested in pride in the past and present of the motherland, in sorrow and concern for its future, in defense of its interests. Historically, it is known that when a nation wants to insult or trample another nation, first of all, it has conquered and destroyed or expelled from its homeland. There must be no more humiliation and suffering for the nation who saw that their homeland remained in the hands of the enemies. After all, the concepts of Homeland, nationality, religion are dear and sacred to a person from everything. Therefore, in the teachings of our religion, the protection of the motherland and concern for the welfare of the nation are also widely covered in the hadiths of the Prophet Sallallahu alayhi wasallam. It is not humanity to leave the homeland to save their lives when a hard day comes to the head of the people.

There is also a proverb in our people that says "be a gado in your land until you become a king in another land". A person who has forgotten others, thinking about his peace of mind, will never be faithful to his motherland, to his people. In

Islam, the concept of Homeland is comprehensive, first of all it is used in the sense of a settlement, that is, housing. The teaching of Islam states that it is one of the greatest deeds that a person protects the homeland, religion, family, where he lives. Standing in the ranks of the military for the protection of the motherland is also considered a great act of merit in our religion. The Prophet salallahu alayhi vasallam said: "it is better than a month of fasting and a night of prayer, which is kept in the face of the enemy." One of the scribes said: "it is known to everyone that in the world of life there are four things that man loves most, that are precious, that are valuable. Those who do not possess these four things are deprived of the honor of humanity. They are: freedom and freedom, the possession of the goods found by Labor, the Motherland where she was born and raised, and her sacred religion, which has been preserved for centuries."

The judges say, "one's fidelity is known from his grief for his homeland, his longing for his brothers, and his longing for the moments of his life that Zoe has taken away". The loyalty and dedication of a person to his people should encourage him to protect his homeland, to find progress and be strong and powerful in every way, and to contribute at the opportunity to the peaceful and prosperous life of his people.

On the way to protect the motherland from various mercenary currents and evil forces, fast-preventive measures aimed at combating religious extremism and its various manifestations, ensuring the safety of citizens were paid off, and significantly positive indicators were achieved.

From the very first days of our country's independence, attention has been increased to young people who are the owners of our future. The comprehensive work carried out in our country is important in educating the owners of our future in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, to the ideas of national independence.

However, today's descendants of the people who have made a huge contribution to world civilization in the past, it is worth noting the recognition of their heritage by World peoples, after all, such feelings in them lead to national pride and spiritual perfection, strengthen their desire to realize their national identity.

Military patriotic education gives a good result only when it is carried out in a picture inextricably linked with physical education. Therefore, military patriotic education cannot be imagined without physical education. Being resistant to cold and heat, not succumbing to diseases quickly, overcoming difficulties, volition. the role of physical education and sports games in the development of qualities inherent in the defender of the Fatherland, such as perseverance, the ability to act

quickly and dexterously, in students – young people and teachers is incredibly great.

The need to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, to prepare them physically and spiritually for the defense of the Motherland is one of the urgent tasks of the present day.

Training of students in general educational institutions, secondary special and secondary vocational educational institutions, including students and young people studying in higher education institutions in the spirit of military patriotism, is now carried out through all systems of educational work.

In fact, genuine loyalty to the motherland also requires being able to protect it. Education of students in the spirit of military patriotism is the main place of all kinds of functioning educational institutions.

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